

Nigerian Twitter (X) Users' Discursive Strategies on the New National Anthem

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Abstract

The researchers examined how Twitter (X) users in Nigeria construct and contest the meaning of national identity and patriotism in the context of the new national anthem. The study utilised the Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) to analyse Twitter (X) posts and comments to identify discursive strategies employed by users to negotiate and contest the meaning of national identity and patriotism. The findings revealed that Twitter users in Nigeria employ various discursive strategies, including articulations of national pride, critiques of government policies, and debates about national values, to construct and contest national identity and patriotism. Findings also showed that power dynamics and social relationships shape the construction and contestation of national identity and patriotism on Twitter (X), with some users exercising more influence than others in shaping the discourse. However, the government actor's engagement on the issue could have been more extensive, and strategies needed to be improved to educate Nigerians on the need for change. It was recommended that the government engage citizens in different social media discourses as they will help educate citizens on government policies and laws.

Keywords: Online Discourse, New Anthem, Twitter (X), Power dynamics, Digital Culture

Introduction

The media has been seen as the guardian of society, responsible for providing essential information and monitoring the actions of those in power, which is crucial for democracy and good governance. Paradoxically, social media can be seen as a tool for widespread expression and a means for society to monitor itself (Daniel & Ifeduba, 2024). The ability of social media to generate, distribute and consume information is essential for democracy and effective governance if appropriately used. In its 1999 Constitution, Nigeria included the principles of good governance as crucial criteria for democratic governance, following the example of many other democratic states. The emergence of the Internet as a dominant medium in the twenty-first century has significantly transformed the media environment. Due to the rapidity, affordability, and extensive reach of information dissemination, there is equitable availability for producing and consuming news (Goodness *et al* 2022).

In early 2024, statistics show that Nigeria had 103.0 million internet users at the start of 2024, with 45.5% internet penetration and 36.75 million social media users in January 2024, constituting 16.2% of the total population (Kemp, 2024). According to advertising resources published in X's resources, Twitter (X) reported 5.75 million users in Nigeria, equivalent to 2.5% of the total population (Kemp, 2024).

The Nigerian government's proposal to change the national anthem and its subsequent implementation generated widespread discussion and debate on social media, mainly X. X provided an online discourse platform and a unique opportunity for citizens to engage with and make sense of national issues and construct and contest meaning around national identity and patriotism. Twitter users aired their opinions, perspectives, and experiences, creating a rich dataset for analysing the discursive strategies employed by citizens to negotiate and make sense of the change (Oyewole *et al* 2025; Izevbaye *et al* 2024).

According to Abubakar (2024), the debate on Nigeria's national anthem change on Twitter involves criticism of governance, emotional appeal and discontent over the process. Users argue that the change diverges from pressing issues like corruption and economic problems. They also express national pride or nostalgia for the old anthem "Nigeria, We Hail Thee," which was rather a symbolisation of a more unifying national identity. Some users outright expressed frustration about the absence of public consultation and questioned the transparency and legitimacy of the decision (Abubakar, 2024).

Several researchers (Ihebuzor & Egbunike, 2018; Adjei, 2016; Smith, 2019) have studied communication on social media, with discourse analysts generally agreeing that computer-mediated platforms allow room for varied forms of socio-political, socio-cultural, and socio-linguistic discourse. This discourse is predominantly about expressing opinions and engaging in ideological conflicts (Chandrasegaran & Kong, 2016; Mohammed *et al* 2017). According to Mohammed *et al* (2017), people often express their "stance" towards particular organisations by making posts on social media platforms such as Twitter (X), Instagram and blogs. Furthermore, notable Nigerian analysts specialising

in discourse analysis on social media, including Ihebuzor & Egbunike (2018), have explored the importance of stance-taking on Twitter in relation to Nigerian political discourse. They also posited that the Nigerian Twitter community acts as a virtual hub for other communities besides those concerned with literature, football, and more. Hence, this research aimed to investigate Nigerian Twitter (X) Users' Discursive Strategies on the new national anthem.

Statement of the Problem

Though the debate concerning the alteration was fervently discussed amongst residents with numerous people airing their views on social media, mainly Twitter (X), there is secrecy about the discursive methods employed by Nigerian Twitter (X) users while discussing the new national song. While some researchers (Ihebuzor & Egbunike, 2018; Adjei, 2016; Mohammed *et al* 2017) have studied public discussions of national identity and social media use in Nigeria, none has principally considered the discursive strategies employed by Nigerian Twitter (X) users in reaction to the new national anthem.

The study seeks to fill this gap in empirical research by analysing the discursive strategies Nigerian Twitter users employ while discussing the new anthem, as well as the discourse on national identity and patriotism engaged by the government on Twitter. Most studies discuss Twitter data from a qualitative perspective, generally performing content analysis of the data as it relates to social media use, without considering Twitter as a medium for public discourse concerning national identity and patriotism. The study scrutinised how Nigerian Twitter users reacted to the new anthem, analysing the discursive strategies being employed in online discourse. It is motivated by the need to understand the role of social media in shaping public opinion and national identity.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Identify and analyse the discursive strategies employed by Nigerian Twitter users in discussing the new national anthem.
2. Assess the effectiveness of the government's engagement on Twitter regarding national identity and patriotism.

Literature Review

Twitter (X)

As a social media platform, Twitter (X) has specific characteristics that define its identity. Having a 140-character constraint on Twitter discussions influences the style and manner in which they are conducted. The form of involvement on Facebook allows users more freedom and space than X. X has many notable advantages over other social media sites, including frequent media updates, the ability to provide immediate information, and a solid following of celebrities. The design of Twitter is particularly well-suited for sharing media updates since it allows for concise messages of just 140

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characters, enabling quick dissemination of news. The comprehensive press releases may be sent at a later time. Furthermore, the distinguishing characteristic of Twitter compared to other social media platforms is its ability to provide immediate updates and information. Users can observe, document, and provide their opinions on worldwide occurrences with nearly no delay" (Balam, 2017). Twitter offers celebrities and public figures a quick and straightforward venue to inform people about accurate news or lifestyle updates, promote their companies, and get more followers. This aspect further shows X's distinctiveness. The site boasts a substantial user base of celebrities and public figures. X is the preferred social media platform for those who want to keep up with celebrities. (Goodness *et al* 2022).

National Anthem

In the 18th century, national anthems gained prominence. One of the earliest known national anthem is the French national anthem. The anthem, written by Claude Joseph Rouget de Lisle in 1792, was adopted as the national anthem on July 14, 1795. It was a war song during the French Revolution, celebrated for its chivalry and popularising the revolutionary triad of liberty, equality, and brotherhood. The American National Anthem, "The Star-Spangled Banner," was inspired by the victory over the British at Fort McHenry in 1812. It celebrates elements of American character, such as independence, bravery, and heroism. The lyricist, Scott Key, provided the poem's tune, which was officially adopted as the American National Anthem in 1931 (Izevbaye *et al* 2024; Oladipupo *et al* 2021).

National Discourse and Social Media

The media has become a crucial tool for democracy and effective government, with information generation, distribution, and consumption functions considered essential. Social media, particularly Twitter, has become a 21st-century instrument of mass expression and a watchdog for democracy and good governance. Now the internet's development has provided equal access for the formation and consumption of news. The unique features of Twitter, such as a limitation of 140 characters for chat, media update, immediacy, and the celebrity cult, make it more amenable to media updates. Thus, one can literally see, report, and comment on events all over the world in real-time. It has become a platform where celebrities and public figures can easily deliver news to the public on the go. Five Nigerian politicians in Nigeria are honored with so-called Superstar statuses on Twitter, namely Reuben Abati, Nasir El-Rufai, Femi Fani-Kayode, Atiku Abubakar, and Obiageli Ezekwesili. These figures have been utilized for political discourse, whereby the immediacy power of Twitter has been harnessed by the politicians, political analysts, and active Nigerian populace. So, it is pertinent to examine the roles the media has played along the lines of constructing good governance in Nigeria (Goodness *et al* 2021).

National discourse comprises all processes in which opinions or arguments are exchanged among people, policymakers, and other stakeholders on issues of paramount national interest. Social media has revolutionised the national conversation by allowing

for the fast spread of information, giving more weight to many perspectives, and fostering global interconnectedness. Therefore, platforms like X (Twitter), Facebook, and Instagram have become the 21-century agoras where the populace engages in discussions, forms, or casts public opinion, while at times organising political actions (Oyewole *et al* 2025; Ihebuzor & Egbunike, 2018). National conversation is one primary avenue of human interactions whereby dialogue and information exchanges are held regarding governance, values, mores and the good life. Participation in any of the topics may arise from several factors, such as psychological, sociological, economic, technological, and structural. Social interaction, national unity, and identity can be crucial elements that draw people toward political conversations. National discourse and engagement exist only when people have opportunities to publicly air their views freely and openly without the threat of clampdown. The more views are allowed to exist freely within a democracy and be reconciled through difference and conflict, the better for good governance. Talk or national conversation is the usual way an individual tests the acceptance or rejection of his ideas before others. However, disruptive, intolerant, or hostile spaces may lead to minority opinions keeping silent due to shame or fear of the majority's reaction (Adelabu *et al* 2024; Ihebuzor *et al* 2018).

Social media has facilitated the democratisation of national discourse by enabling people to circumvent conventional intermediaries and actively engage in public discussions. Hashtag campaigns, online petitions, and social media movements have become potent instruments for galvanising public sentiment and shaping policy determinations. Nevertheless, social media exacerbates echo chambers, misinformation, and polarisation, presenting obstacles to productive public dialogue. The convergence of national discourse and social media prompts significant enquiries over the impact of technology on moulding public sentiment, political participation, and national sense of self. With the ongoing development of social media, it is crucial to analyse its influence on national discussions, namely how it either supports or obstructs inclusive, well-informed, and courteous public exchanges (Alade & Daniel, 2024; Adjei *et al* 2016).

Context and content of conversations are essential in determining their prevalence, quality, and depth. When surrounded by people who share the same opinion, an echo chamber occurs, with opinions expressed being mutually reinforcing and barely conflictual. However, disagreements are essential for democracy's growth and development. Social media, such as Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, and Twitter, empower citizens to engage in and expand the space and domains for political discourse. These platforms allow digital citizens to carry on political discourse from their private spaces, making them able to make invasions and incursions into public domains with their message (Oladipupo, 2021)

A functionalist view of political engagement suggests that people engage in conversations because the rewards of participating far outweigh the losses, discomforts, or inconveniences that derive from it. Rewards could include increased self-worth, improved popularity, increased following the more incredible popularity of a political view or party, or a sense of gain over a political rival. (Oyewole *et al* 2025; Alade & Daniel, 2024; Izevbaye *et al* 2024).

Theoretical framework

Public Sphere

Jürgen Habermas formulated the public sphere theory, which pertains to the domain of public discussion, where individuals participate in logical argumentation and thoughtful consideration of matters of shared interest (Lanneau, 2020). Habermas (2006) defines a public sphere as a domain in our social existence where a semblance of public opinion may be formed (p.49). The notion of the public sphere emphasises the significance of inclusive, logical, and polite discussions in forming public opinion and impacting policy choices (Habermas, 2006). X and similar social media platforms have broadened the scope of public discourse, allowing individuals to engage in national dialogues and influence public sentiment.

Smith (2019) states that X is a social media platform that allows recognised and anonymous users to express their opinions on any topic using concise words. This social network has gained significant recognition, becoming a favoured medium for individuals to express their ideas. Twitter allows individuals to freely share their opinions on any topic, regardless of its significance, therefore fostering a democracy 2.0 that upholds the principle of freedom of speech for everyone. This social networking platform is renowned for its commitment to openness since it implements few restrictions (Goodness *et al* 2022). However, this regulation can result in misconduct since individuals with malicious intent might propagate hazardous or unlawful concepts. Although Twitter provides users with the ability to report accounts or tweets that include racism, homophobia, violence, harassment, and other objectionable content, many people are still able to see these offensive "opinions" before they are ever removed. Moreover, several individuals see Twitter as very noxious, primarily due to its fundamental objective of enabling individuals to express their viewpoints. Without a private account, anyone can remark on a user's tweets and interfere in their personal affairs, resulting in an unwelcome invasion of privacy. Furthermore, Twitter is sometimes used to uncover individuals' antiquated (and contentious) tweets and then discredit them by declaring them "cancelled." While Twitter is often seen as the epitome of a digital public sphere, it is crucial to maintain a critical perspective on this social network and acknowledge that incessantly expressing one's opinions may not always be advantageous for the recipient (Alade & Daniel, 2024; Smith, 2019).

This study uses the public sphere theory to examine the discursive strategies employed by Nigerian Twitter users when discussing the new national anthem. The theory provides a framework for understanding how online discussions reflect and shape public opinion on national issues. By analysing the language, tone and themes used by Twitter users, this study sheds light on the ways in which social media shapes national identity and public opinion in Nigeria

Methodology

The researchers used the CDA methodological technique, which falls within the qualitative research paradigm. CDA is an interdisciplinary study approach. Unlike

linguistic studies that are concerned with grammatical rules, discourse analysis denies the importance of the contextual facet of words. This approach brings language use to the forefront in relation to attaining certain goals, while also considering the interpersonal factors involved in communication, such as building trust, creating uncertainty, evoking emotion or mitigating conflict. Discourse analysis does not study tiny language components such as tones, words, or phrases; rather, it investigates larger units of language, such as full conversations, texts or collections of texts. The researchers applied discourse analysis to study various perspectives Nigerian Twitter (X) Users hold on the New National Anthem more deeply. The objective was to ascertain the discursive strategies used by Nigerian Twitter (X) Users' on the new National Anthem. (Adelabu et al., 2024; Olarenwaju *et al* 2023; Fairclough & Fairclough, 2013; Merkl-Davies & Koller, 2012).

This research examined a community of non-human populations by analysing the remarks made by users on X about the new national anthem. Given Nigeria's vast number of social media platforms, it is unfeasible to examine comments on the new national anthem across all of them. Therefore, the researchers focused on comments and posts made explicitly on the X. X, which was chosen based on Kemp's (2024) data, indicating that the social media network with the ideal space allows public discourse and discursive strategies with functions like X space. X was deliberately chosen for this study due to its ease of locating and tracking chats using hashtags, simplifying the research process.

This research recorded remarks to demonstrate members' online engagement and communication and their contributions to the discourse or issue on the new national anthem. Due to the impracticability of analysing the comments of every X user about the new national anthem in Nigeria, it is necessary to deliberately choose Oby Ezekwesili's (1.4 million followers) and Shehu Sani's (3.3 million followers) posts as the study corpus is justified because:

- They are prominent influencers with large followings.
- Their posts represent contrasting views on the national anthem change.
- They have generated significant engagement and debate on Twitter.
- They offer diverse perspectives on the issue.
- They are directly relevant to the study topic.
- They are contemporary and reflect current public discourse.

This corpus provides a rich and nuanced understanding of Nigerian Twitter X users' discourse on the new national anthem. The researcher intentionally chose a specific hashtag article from which comments were collected for this study. This item was chosen due to its news story comprehensively documenting the agency's efforts from January 2021 to October 2022.

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Fig 1: Oby Ezekwesili's X handle

Fig 2 Senator Shehu Sani X handle

Result

This data was based on the comments that followed the initial post by Oby Ezekwesili and Shehu Sani. 10 purposively selected comments each were analysed each.

Figure 3: Post by Oby Ezekwesili's Post on May 29 2024

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Figure 4 & 5 comments from Oby's post

Figure 6 &7 Comments from Oby's post

Figure 8 Shehu Sani's Post on May 29 2024

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Figure 9 & 10 Comments from Shehu Sani's post

Discussion

Nigerian Twitter users used rhetorical techniques, humour, and touches of sarcasm to participate in the discussion around the proposed alteration to the national anthem. These techniques included expressions of patriotism, analysis of governmental actions, and deliberations on national principles. Although some of the conversations had elements of

insults, these techniques exemplify the process of debating and bargaining over the interpretation of ideas in the public domain as individuals aimed to influence the storytelling around national identity and loyalty.

The discursive tactics used by Nigerian Twitter users on the new national anthem illustrate the opportunities and difficulties associated with social media in enabling public domain debate. Although social media facilitates the expression of many perspectives and the quick spread of information, it also intensifies the development of closed groups that reinforce existing beliefs, the spread of false information, and the division of society.

Nigerian Twitter users' rhetorical techniques, humour, and sarcasm in discussing the proposed alteration to the national anthem resonate with the concept of the "public sphere", where citizens engage in rational-critical debates to shape public opinion. This online discourse also illustrates the "deliberative democracy" framework, where individuals exchange arguments and counterarguments to reach a shared understanding (Nartey & Yu, 2023, p. 2).

The employment of expressions of patriotism, analysis of governmental actions, and deliberations on national principles reflect the "nation-building" process where individuals negotiate and construct a shared national identity. However, the presence of insults and closed groups reinforces existing beliefs, highlighting the "echo chambers" phenomenon and the challenges of social media in facilitating inclusive public debate (Adjei, 2016, p.560).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that Nigerian Twitter users used diverse rhetorical techniques to discuss a proposed national anthem alteration, demonstrating their active involvement in shaping national identity and loyalty narratives. This highlights opportunities (diverse perspectives, rapid information dissemination) and challenges (echo chambers, misinformation, and societal division) associated with online public domain debates. This study, from its findings, recommended thus:

1. Promoting National Identity and Loyalty through Online Discussions.
2. Encourage diverse, inclusive discussions for comprehensive understanding.
3. Implement fact-checking mechanisms and media literacy initiatives to combat misinformation.
4. Promote cross-platform engagement and interdisciplinary approaches for nuanced understanding.
5. Support research on social media's role in shaping public opinion.
6. Develop strategies to counteract social media's potential to reinforce beliefs.

References

Abubakar, M. (2024, May 29). Outrage as Nigeria changes national anthem. *BBC*. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c3gg7z0n4jxo>

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- Adelabu, O. T., Olanihun, S. Z., Daniel, H. A., Olawuwo, G. O., Okoji, C. T. & Oladipupo, A. A. (2024). Analyzing President Tinubu's speech on economic challenges: A critical discourse analysis of persuasive tools. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Linguistics, Marketing and Communication (IJLMC)*, 11(3), 1-11.
- Adjei, J. K. (2016, October). The role of social media in national discourse and mobilisation of citizens. In *2016 International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Systems (CTS)* (pp. 559-563). IEEE.
- Alade, M. O. & Daniel, H. A. (2024). Skit Influencers Marketing as a Predictor of Sports Betting Intentions among Male Undergraduates of Bowen University, Nigeria. *Icheke Journal of the Faculty of Humanities*, 22(1), 151-160.
- Daniel, H. A. & Ifeduba, E. (2024). Social media prank: A dangerous phenomenon militating against media credibility. *Journal of Behavioural Studies*, 5(1), 1-6.
- Goodness, R. O., Onor, K. C., Sandra, G. T. & Folarin, S. F. (2022). Twitter ban in Nigeria: A stigma to democratic governance. *Perspektif*, 11(3), 821-828.
- Habermas, J. (2006). The public sphere: An encyclopedia article. In M.G. Durham & D.M. Kellner (Eds.), *Media and Cultural Studies*, (pp. 73-78). London: Blackwell.
- Ihebuzor, N. & Egbunike, N. (2018). Twitter as a tool of political discourse in Nigeria: Dialogue, self-aggrandisement or party politicking? *Namibia Planned Parenthood Association (NAPPA)*, Namibia.
- Izevbaye, D., Adeniran, K. & Ayoade, J. (2024, June 17). Purpose and practice of National Anthem. *The Punch*. Retrieved from <https://punchng.com/purpose-and-practice-of-national-anthem/>
- Kemp, S. (2024, February 23). Digital 2024: Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-nigeria>
- Lanneau, C. (2020, November 25). Twitter: An ideal public sphere? Retrieved from <https://blogs.fasos.maastrichtuniversity.nl/digitalcultures-MA/students/clanneau20/2020/11/25/twitter-an-ideal-public-sphere/>
- Oladipupo, S. L. (2021). The metaphysical implications of the Nigerian national anthem and pledge. *Makurdi Owl Journal of Philosophy (MAJOP)*, 2(1) 102-117.
- Olanrewaju, M. M., Talabi, F. O., Sanusi, B. O., Adelabu, O. O., Ayomide, J. F., Bello, S. A., & Oloyede, D. B. (2023). Social media comments on Nigeria's NDLEA war against drug abuse and propensity to reduce drug peddling. *Journal of African Films and Diaspora Studies*, 6(2), 75-83.
- Oyewole, J. A., Ayo-Obiremi, I. T., Daniel, H. A., Ojemola, A. M., Nwogwugwu, D. I., & Ayantade, J. B. (2025). COVID-19 and Social Responsibility Reportage in Selected Nigerian Newspapers. *International Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Scope*, 6(1), 1065-1072.
- Smith, N. (2019). *Exploring the role of Twitter as a public sphere that facilitates civil discourse* [Dissertation, Technological University Dublin]
- Nartey, M., & Yu, Y. (2023). A discourse analytic study of #FixTheCountry on Ghanaian Twitter. *Social Media Society*, 9(1), 20563051221147328.